

Research Article**Outcome of Chronic Occlusion Restoration by Percutaneous
Coronary Intervention****¹Hina Fatima, ²Afsheen Fatima, ³Makia Khursheed
and ⁴Ali Arshad**¹WMO DHQ Teaching Hospital, Lahore.²Block No. 61, New Model Town, Dera Ghazi Khan³R/O Basti Dosa P/O Basti Shah Ali DGK⁴Medical Officer, RHC Basirpur, Okara**ABSTRACT****Objective:** To evaluate the technical success of percutaneous coronary intervention (PCI) in chronic total occlusion (CTO).**Materials and methods:** This observational study was conducted between February 2016 to February 2017 in the cardiology department of Chaudhry Pervaiz Elahi Institute of Cardiology, Multan. Seventy patients who met the criteria of union and exclusion were included in the study. All CTO PCIs were made by experienced cardiologists. A 30 minute fluoroscopic time was assigned to ligate the lesion. The primary end point was the success of the procedures. The procedure was abandoned and failed if the angioplasty had progressed or if there was a secondary endpoint with complications such as coronary dissection, perforation or hemodynamic instability. The procedure has been concluded on the achievement of either the primary endpoint or any of the secondary endpoints.**Findings:** Mean age of the patients was 52.7 ± 9.9 years, mean height was 167.22 ± 6.4 cm, mean weight was 76.3 ± 9 kg. 57 (81.4%) of the 70 patients were male and 13 (18.6%) were female. 22 (31.4%) were diabetic, 39 (55.7%) were hypertensive, 34 (48.6%) were smokers and 17 (24.3%) were family history in terms of coronary artery risk factors. Ischemic heart disease and 13 (13%) had a history of ischemic heart disease. The diseased artery was left in 32 (45.7%) patients with anterior descending (LAD), 9 (12.9%) with left circumflex (LCX) and 29 (41.4%) with right coronary artery (RCA). Distal vessels were seen in 56 patients (80%) in terms of CTO lesion characteristics, antegrade flow 45 (64.3%), retrograde flow 25 (35.7%) and calcification 9 (12.9%). The stump shape contracted in 46 (65.7%) and 24 (34.3%). There were collateral collaterals in 36 (51.4%) cases, bridge collaterals in 13 (18.6%) and less than 2 mm lateral branches in 42 mm (60%) lesions. The length of the lesion was <10 mm in 4 patients (5.7%), 10-20 mm (42.9%) in 30 patients and 20 mm in 36 (51.4%) patients. The guide wire passed through 54 (77%) patient lesions with balloon support. Thrombolysis (TIMI) III flow in myocardial infarction was 54 (77%) and technical success was 54 (77%). The remaining 30% were observed in 16 patients (22.9%).**Conclusion:** Percutaneous coronary intervention is a safe and useful method for revascularization of coronary chronic total occlusion lesions. In addition, the radial artery may be a favorable vascular pathway in PCI for CTO.**Key words:** Chronic total occlusion; coronary artery disease; Percutaneous coronary intervention; Slim fit, Collateral Bridges.**INTRODUCTION**

Chronic total occlusion (CTO) coronary artery bypass surgery (PCI) is one of the major challenges in interventional cardiology. It was stabilized. The actual prevalence of CTO in the general population is unknown, because a

proportion of patients with CTO are asymptomatic or minimally symptomatic and never enter coronary angiography. CTO is a common problem seen in 10-30% of PCI patients. The accepted indication for the recanalization of a chronic

coronary occlusion is ischemic symptoms related to the occluded vein or inducible ischemia. Recanalization of the chronic total coronary occlusion has a positive effect on survival, relieving angina and improving left ventricular function. The primary success rate is relatively low because the recanalization of the CTO is a complicated procedure because it can not pass through the obstruction. In addition, the overall procedure and duration of fluoroscopy are more prolonged and the use of the equipment is greater than the PCI of non-occluded veins and has a high recurrence rate. PCI can be performed with a success rate of 88.9-90.8% of chronic coronary occlusions, but with a higher restenosis rate than the angioplasty of non-occlusive vessels. This study was designed to assess the outcome of PCI in CTO injuries in terms of technical success. In addition, factors that lead to a successful PCI, namely, conical stump, to identify the least lost segment. This study will clarify the understanding of PCI to the CTO in terms of selecting the patients who should benefit best from the intervention and who should not be intervened. The PCI success has been shown to reduce improve left ventricular ejection fraction, anginal symptoms, reduce coronary bypass graft surgery (CABG) need and prolong life span.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This observational study was conducted between February 2016 to February 2017 in the cardiology department of Chaudhry Pervaiz Elahi Institute of Cardiology, Multan. Seventy patients were studied after receiving the study criteria and informed consent. All patients were described about the study protocol. Patients were included using a probabilistic sampling technique. All patients with chronic total occlusion were included with a 0-1 TIMI flow to the PCI. Patients with renal dysfunction were excluded from high serum creatinine > 1.4 mg / dL, previous PKG history, previous CABG history. Chronic total occlusion was defined as natural coronary artery occlusion without lumen persistence and TIMI 0-1 current. The duration of occlusion should be 3 months or

more predicted from clinical events such as myocardial infarction, sudden onset or worsening of symptoms or previous angiography. Technical success was defined as the restoration of the third degree TIMI flow with residual stenosis <30% on coronary angiography. All patients received 600 mg clopidogrel loading plus 150 mg / d aspirin and 75 mg / d for 9 months. During the procedure intravenous heparin was applied. All CTO PCIs were performed by an experienced cardiologist. Local anesthesia was performed in the arterial puncture area.

A 30-minute fluoroscopic time was reserved to ligate the lesion. If the angioplasty is progressing or complications such as coronary dissection, perforation or hemodynamic instability occur, the procedure is abandoned and reported as unsuccessful. The choice of angioplasty guide wires and support balloons is at the discretion of PCI operators. Operators progressed from soft to hard cabling. Balloon placement was done before placement of the stent. The stent was at the doctor's discretion. Pure metal and drug delivery endoprocesses of 8-18 mm length and available lengths of 2.5, 3.0 and 3.5 mm in diameter were used. The next dilatation was performed to optimize the angiographic distribution. The procedure has been concluded on the achievement of either the primary endpoint or any of the secondary endpoints. The main purpose of the work was the success of the procedures. The sequelae endpoint is guidewire lesion, perforation, dissection, peri-procedural instability or death.

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

The data was analyzed in SPSS 13.0 version. Nominal variables are shown as frequency and percent, and continuous variables are expressed as mean $\pm$ standard deviation. Significance tests were not performed because it was an observational study.

RESULTS

The mean age of the patients studied was 52.7 $\pm$ 9.9 years, mean height was 167.22 $\pm$ 6.4 cm and mean weight was 76.3 $\pm$ 9 kg. 57 of the 70

patients (81.4%) were male and 13 (18.6) were female. 22 (31.4%) were diabetic, 39 (55.7%) were hypertensive, 34 (48.6%) were smokers and 17 (24.3%) were family history in terms of coronary artery risk factors. Ischemic heart disease and 13 (13%) previous stories. Ischemic Heart Disease The diseased artery was left in the anterior descending (LAD) in 32 (45.7%) patients, the left circumflex (LCX) in 9 (12.9%) and the right coronary artery (RCA) in 29. , 4%) patients. Distal vessels were seen in 56 patients (80%) in terms of CTO lesion characteristics, antegrade flow 45 (64.3%), retrograde flow 25 (35.7%) and calcification 9 (12.9%). JR Guider in the PCG of RCA lesions and XB 3 Guider in the left system were used. The predictors of successful PKG, ie stump shape, contracted in 46 (65.7%) and 24 (34.3%) planes. Table 2.

LAD=Left anterior descending; LCX=Left circumflex; RCA=Right coronary artery

Table 2. Angiographic lesion characteristics of CTO

VARIABLES	NUMBERS (PERCENTAGES) (n=70)
Distal vessels visualized	56 (80%)
Antegrade flow	45(64.3%)
Retrograde flow	25(35.7%)
Calcification	9(12.9%)

Collaterals were found in 36 (51.4%), 13 (18.6%) collateral bridges, and 42 (60%) patients were found to be 2 mm from the obstruction zone. The length of the lesion was <10 mm in 4 patients (5.7%), 10-20 mm (42.9%) in 30 patients and 20 mm in 36 (51.4%) patients. The guide wire passed the balloon support with lesion at level 54 (77%). TIMI III flow was achieved in 54 patients (77%) and technical success was 54 (77%) and 16 patients (22.9%) had residual stenosis of 30%. Table 4

DISCUSSION

In the present study, the procedural success rate is 77%. The PCI success rate was higher than the success rates reported in meta-analyzes (53-68%) (9), but probably similar to the 70-75% reported by some authors, 10-13 Chronic late lesions were

higher in the current study. Puma et al.¹⁴ reported that successful intervention of chronicity in the meta-analyzes was the most important predictor and that the success rate in late chronic obstruction was significantly lower than early chronic obstruction. In our study, the factors affecting the success of transradial PCI for the CTO were similar to those of the previous reports. Although the success of a CTO intervention depends on the operator's experience, the type of injury and indications for intervention, the devices used for the procedure for the outcome, especially in the case of transradial intervention, have critical prescription. . When radial approach is used for CTO intervention, the availability of adequate guidance support becomes a major problem, since it is usually not possible to use a guide catheter larger than Fr. As a result, intervention is generally preferred. The transtoral coronary artery is better than the transradial PCI for CTO, as a 7 or 8 Fr guide catheter can be used to obtain more support when compared to the s6 Fr guide catheter, which is often used in the transductive approach. However, since the catheter materials have developed so much and there is a specific curvature to increase the support, in most cases we could obtain sufficient guidance support with a guide catheter.

In this study, the choice of guide catheters is based on the characteristics of the lesion and the size of the radial artery. Often a guide catheter was used at 6 Fr, guide catheter types used for CTO were similar to those needed for transradial PKG for other coronary lesions. In our study, transradial PKG was 58.6% for a CTO lesion using XB 3.0 guiding catheters while the lesion was in the left coronary artery and 41.4%. Judkins' right guide catheter was used for lesions in the right coronary artery. Judetta et al. Compared to the results reported by Judkins, the catheter was less used in the correct guidance. The authors reported that Judkins (JL) lead catheters were used in 49% of left coronary artery cases and used a 57% Judkins (JR) guiding catheter for the right coronary artery. Transradial ICP. Kim and colleagues evaluated the feasibility of transradial coronary intervention

(CRT) in 85 consecutive CTO patients. Clinical, angiographic and procedural factors were compared between success and failure groups. The overall success rate was 65.5% (57/87 lesions) with ICRT and failure was the most common cause of inability to pass lesion with a guide wire. A highly variable analysis showed that the most important predictor of failure was the time of congestion. The success rate of the procedures has been increased with the use of the new generation hydrophilic wires. The guide catheter 6F was used in most cases 70 (81%). In both cases, due to the severe case of subclavian curvature and radial artery loop in one case, the guiding catheter was inserted into the coronary ostium and the angulation of the femoral artery approached the femoral artery. No major complications were seen in the entrance area.

Park et al¹⁸ reported that total obstructive lesion of 195 patients. In 134 patients, percutaneous coronary intervention was attempted in 134 total occlusion lesions. Successful rechallenge with 89 lesion stent implantation was performed and the success rate was 66.4%. A process-related death occurred because of the fact that there was no reflow. Q and T wave inversions were observed in 60 (32.1%) and 78 patients (41.7%), respectively, after 8 patients with branch block were excluded. The presence of Q waves was associated with severe angina, decreased left ventricular ejection fraction, abnormality of regional wall motion, and reversal of T wave, but the procedure was not associated with success. Percutaneous coronary intervention is a safe and useful method for revascularization of chronic total coronary occlusion lesions. The success rate of the procedure was not related to the presence of pathological Q waves associated with severe angina and decreased left ventricular function.

Hoye and⁸⁸⁵ CTO reported a total of 874 consecutive patients treated for injury. Mean follow-up was 4.47 + 2.69 years. Patients were evaluated for the occurrence of major adverse cardiac events (MACE) involving death, acute myocardial infarction and coronary artery bypass surgery or revascularization with PCI. At 576

lesions (65.1%), successful revascularization was achieved and a stent was implanted at 81%. At day 30, the overall MACE rate is significantly lower in patients with successful renalization. The 5-year survival rate was significantly higher in patients with successful revascularization. In addition, there was a significantly greater free survival of the MACE, and many of the events reflected the need to repeat the intervention. There were no independent predictors for survival, successful revascularization, minimal age and diabetes mellitus, and multivessel disease. The authors concluded that a CTO successfully performed percutaneous revascularization resulting in a significantly improved rate of survival and a decrease in adverse events greater than 5 years. Much of the events relate to the need for repetition, and the introduction of drug-eluting stents with low restenosis rates encourages the development of technologies to improve the success rates of recanalization. However, an unsuccessful recalcination can be acutely associated with a negative event, and new technologies should focus on a safe approach to successful recanalization.

CONCLUSION

Percutaneous coronary intervention is a safe and useful method for revascularization of chronic total coronary occlusions. In addition, the radial artery may be a vascular pathway that is feasible with a successful procedure for coronary interventions for CTO and the absence of any complication of access.

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